

Practices, Disposal, And Utilization of Scrap Fabrics from Dressmakers/Tailors for Household Items and Environmental Sustainability in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State

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Abstract: The study utilized fabric scraps from tailors to produce household items for family use and ensure environmental sustainability in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State, Nigeria. Four objectives and four research questions guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used. The total population for the study was made up of 552 respondents, consisting of 360 tailors, 96 farmers, and 96 ESWAMA staff in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State. A sample of 92 respondents were drawn using purposive sampling techniques. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Data generated from the study were analyzed using percentages. The study revealed eight ways dressmakers/tailors handle scrap fabrics, which include the use of scrap fabrics in making patchworks, among others. Four ways dressmakers /tailors dispose the scrap fabrics which include disposing them in the waste bin among others were also identified. Six possible outcomes of indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabrics, which include that scrap fabrics cause environmental pollution, cause drainage blockage, and can lead to other health issues, among others. The household items produced were assessed in terms of originality (96.7), uniqueness (80.4), utility (78.3), durability (83.5), neatness (84.8), and finishing (95.5). It was concluded that a very good way of managing the scrap fabric is by producing useful household items that will not only preserve our environment but also provide financial benefits for the family when the household items are sold. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the environmental authorities in Nigeria should map out a disposal site strictly for collecting fabric waste, to enable the reuse of the scrap fabrics among others.

Keywords: Dressmaking/Tailoring, dressmakers/tailors, environmental sustainability, household items, and scrap fabric.

1. Introduction

Dressmaking and tailoring are aspects of Clothing and Textile in Home Economics program. Clothing and Textile is a major area of Home Economics program that prepares students towards self-reliance in creativity and artistic skills. Popular Clothing and Textiles careers include: dressmaking/tailoring, fashion designing, embroidery making, textile merchandising, fashion merchandising, teaching, modelling, haberdashery sales, textile retailing, textile production, interior decoration, weaving, dyeing, laundry, and clothing repairs (Forster, 2020). Dressmaking is the craft of sewing clothes and dresses, while tailoring, on the other hand, is the act of making, mending, or altering clothes, especially suits, coats, and outer garments. A dressmaker is a person who makes custom clothing for women, such as dresses, blouses, and evening gowns. Also, a tailor is a person who makes, repairs, or alters clothes professionally, especially suits and men's clothing. The difference between a tailor and a dressmaker is primarily their clientele; a dressmaker specializes in clothes for women, and a tailor makes clothes for men. Males and females have different body shapes that call for a different approach to pattern making, garment cutting, and construction (Sensis, 2019).. For the purpose of this study, dressmaking and tailoring will be used interchangeably as both refers to the process of producing clothes.

Recently many persons have gone into tailoring/dressmaking for reasons like creative passion, economic opportunity, sustainable clothing solutions, interest, underemployment, better ways they can expand their income, unemployment among others. Kavitha and Sagar (2022) noted that in recent decades, people are demanding for more personalized tailors in the stitching industry and requirement for more customized cloths are in great demand. Supporting this, Martindale & Mckinney (2019) also noted that garment sewing is undergoing a resurgence in participation, with a growing number of women choosing to sew their clothes instead of buying readily available fast fashion. Also there has been an increase in the demand of custom made clothes. To this regard, Ekholm & Frisk, (2019) noted that people prefer custom made clothes than casual wears when going for parties. Unemployment in Nigeria is another factor that tend to make people equip themselves with saleable skills. In this regard, Erim, Okon & Ojong (2023) highlighted the importance of skill acquisition as a powerful mechanism for mitigating high unemployment rates in the society. One of these skills that can be acquired is

dressmaking/ tailoring. However, a greater percentage chose to learn how to sew thus increasing the number of dressmakers/tailors in Nigeria. These reasons have significantly gained a huge rise in the number of dressmaker/tailors found especially in Nsukka LGA.

Tailors/dressmakers cut and sew people's clothes. These processes are termed clothing construction processes. Clothing construction processes include pattern making, laying out, cutting out, sewing, and finishing, among others. However, Bans-Akutey, Aboagyewaa-Ntiri & Appiah (2024) maintained that freehand cutting and pattern making remain the bedrock of ways of designing garments in the fashion industry. Freehand cutting, according to Momoh (2021), is the process of drafting designs and directly cutting them out on the fabric without the use of patterns. In addition, Bakker-Edoh (2018) also defined freehand cutting as a methodology used by dressmakers and tailors in apparel making, where individual body measurements are used as a guide when cutting directly on the fabric. In Nigeria, precisely Nsukka town, it is common for tailors and dressmakers to engage in free hand cutting. Free hand cutting has many advantages as well as disadvantages. One of the advantages is that it helps in the mastery of dressmaking/ tailoring skills. In contrast, the disadvantages include having many variations, no set standard method or instruction for teaching, and production of lots of fabric waste. The fabric waste produced usually will not be used in making up the garment; these fabric wastes are termed scrap fabrics.

A scrap is typically a small item that was originally part of something larger, like a scrap of fabric that was once part of a larger piece. Scrap fabric is a small piece of fabric cut out from the main fabric during garment construction. Scrap fabrics according to Goswami (2022), typically includes the scrap generated in tailor shops from cutting out fabrics, discarded clothing from households, rejected linen from hotels, leftovers from upholstery and home furnishing stores. Scrap fabrics are sometimes referred to as waste fabrics or fabric wastes. This is because they are not used when making up the clothes. Offiong (2018), defined fabric waste as pieces of fabric that are cut out and abandoned by dressmakers when clothes are constructed. The author further noted that clothing construction done by these dressmakers in their shops generate certain amount of waste mainly fabric waste. These scrap fabrics come in various sizes and can be used creatively for various purposes. Mifetu (2021) noted that leftover fabrics can be used for new developments and innovations for financial purposes. On the other hand, if they are not properly managed, they can harm individuals and very dangerous to the the

environment. This is why Owodiong-Idemeko & Barikpe (2016) noted that leftover fabrics can be a source of fuel during a fire outbreak in homes, which can result in loss of lives and properties. Many tailors have attempted to use the bigger scraps to produce some patchwork for outfits like dresses, blouses, skirts, etc., as well as making babies' clothes. It is necessary to note that some of these scrap fabrics are so small and irregular that they cannot be used by tailors for making patchworks, so they dispose of them. Page | 185

Disposal of scrap fabric means getting rid of it as waste. Various practices involved in disposing of fabric scraps by tailors include incinerating them, dumping them in the gutter, disposing of them in the dustbin, and a huge amount littered in the environment, thus they end up in the landfills. Meanwhile, Chirapa & Mberengwa (2021), noted various methods of disposing of scrap fabrics, which include burning, dumping, and thrift work. Each of these methods of disposing of scrap fabric poses a threat to the individual while polluting the environment. Disposing of scrap fabric in the dustbin litters the environment. Rani and Jamal (2018), stated that synthetic fiber products will not decompose in the landfill, while wool does decompose, but they also produce methane, which contributes to global warming. The Council for Textile Recycling estimates that 5% of the waste currently sitting in landfills is textile waste (Bennett, 2014). In this regard, Rani and Jamal (2018) also noted that the textile industry is accused of being one of the most polluting industry, the authors went further to say that clothing manufacturing generates a large amount of textile waste, which ends up in landfills. Meanwhile, disposing of scraps in the gutters helps to fill the gutter, thus causing erosion and environmental degradation. At the same time, incinerating scrap fabric has several disadvantages to the environment, which range from global warming, greenhouse effect, acid rain, among others. The amount of waste generated, and its actual or potential negative effect on the environment, are matters of concern to government and communities at large (Yeboah, 2011). Thus, this research tends to utilize these fabric scraps in producing household items for family use, as well as environmental sustainability in Nsukka LGA.

Sustainability is the avoidance of the depletion of natural resources in order to maintain an ecological balance. Mitchell (2020) stated that sustainability focuses on meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs; the concept of sustainability is composed of three pillars: economic, environment and social. Environmental

sustainability, therefore, is focusing in meeting our needs for water, food, and shelter as well as engaging in activities that make our lives enjoyable, including leisure activities and entertainment, without causing damage to our environment or depleting the resources that cannot be renewed. Fabric scrap if not managed well, can lead to environmental depletion. In line with this, Owodiong-Idemeko & Barikpe (2016) pointed out that scrap fabrics, if not properly disposed of, may constitute environmental problems which include blockage of channels of water, resulting in flooding to the inhabitants. However, Koca (2019) also noted that the waste created by the process of clothing production creates environmental, economic, and ethical issues. Bullman (2007) noted that reducing waste, reusing materials, and recycling is the most powerful way by which individuals, households, institutions, and businesses can protect their communities and the environment. As regards this, El-Nouby, Azzam, Hohamed, and El-sheikl (2005) stated that textile waste can be managed in different ways according to the raw material type and the society's awareness towards the relative environmental problem. Sarita Devi, Vivek Singh, and Parveen Punia (2015) also noted that cutting waste and discarded textile materials can be used in making small items of household use and clothing accessories, or can be recycled. Household items are tangible and movable personal property placed in the living rooms, dining rooms, kitchen, bedroom, bathroom, and other rooms of the home. They include a scatter cushion, a center piece, a bed sheet, and a bin, among others. Therefore, production of household items using the smallest scrap of fabric will not only benefit families but also sustain the environment.

Many studies have been conducted on the use of scrap for producing patchworks for outfits, collages, handmade papers, household clothing items, among others (Hamid & Al Belihy, 2020; Yeboah, 2011; Offiong, 2018). Meanwhile, Rani and Jamal (2018) worked on recycling the scrap fabrics for environmental sustainability. In addition, Tabassum, Abid, and Gulzarin (2021) noted that most textiles can be recycled. Recycling is not a common activity here in Nigeria, and in Nsukka precisely. What remains unanswered in this line of study is what the smallest irregular scrap of fabric can be used for, thereby sustaining our environment, hence the study.

1.1. Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to examine practices, disposal and utilization of fabric scraps from tailors to produce household items for family use and environmental sustainability in Nsukka LGA of

Enugu state Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identify what dressmakers/tailors do with scrap fabric.
2. Find out ways dressmakers/tailors dispose of the scrap fabric.
3. Examine possible outcomes of indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric.
4. Produce a household item using the scrap fabric.

1.2. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1 What do dressmakers/tailors do with scrap fabric?
- 2 What are the ways dressmakers/tailors dispose of the scrap fabric?
- 3 What are the possible outcomes of indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric?
- 4 What is the expert assessment on the suitability of the household items produced from the scrap fabric?

2. Methodology

1.1. Research Design: A descriptive survey design was employed to seek the opinion of the respondents on issues of scrap fabric from tailors in Nsukka LGA of Enugu state.

2.1.1. Area of Study: The area of study was Nsukka LGA of Enugu State. The dwellers are predominantly artisans, traders and civil servants.

2.2. Population for the Study: The population was made up of 552 respondents consisting of 360 tailors, 96 farmers and 96 ESWAMA staff in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State. The population was made up of tailors, farmers and ESWAMA workers, both male and female in the LGA.

2.3. Samples and sampling techniques: Purposive sampling technique was used to select the 92 respondents. Respondents sampled was: 60 tailors, 16 farmers and 16 ESWAMA staff. This is a good percentage of the total population. The 16 farmers and the 16 ESWAMA staff responded to research question 3, while the tailors responded to others.

2.4. Instrument for Data collection: A four-point scale Structured questionnaire called “Issues on scrap fabric Questionnaire (ISFQ), was constructed by the researcher for data collection, the instrument was made up of five sections which are sections A, personal data of the respondents. Section B on uses of scrap fabric by tailors, section C, on ways of disposing scrap fabric, D, on outcomes of

indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabrics and E on assessment of household items produced using scrap fabric. The instrument was validated by three experts. Validity and a reliability co-efficient of 0.89 were obtained using Cronbach's Alpha.

2.5. Data Collection and Analysis Techniques: Face to face method was adopted in administering the questionnaire to the respondents. The questionnaires were distributed to the 92 participants by the researcher with the help of two research assistance who were briefed on how to respond to the questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed using percentage. Scores above 50% were accepted while scores below 50% were rejected. This is the simplest majority threshold

3. Findings of the Study

Table 1: Percentage Distribution on responses of what tailors do with scrap fabrics.

S/N	Item statement	Yes (%)	No (%)	Remark
1.	Fabric scraps are packed in bags and stored in the shop	78.3	21.7	Agreed
2.	Scrap fabrics are used in making patchworks	52.2	47.8	Agreed
3.	Scrap fabrics are used for sewing babies' wears	60.9	39.1	Agreed
4.	Scrap fabrics are recycled	34.4	69.6	Disagreed
5.	Scrap fabrics are sold	34.4	69	Disagreed
6.	Scrap fabrics are used as rags in the shop	65.2	34.8	Agreed
7.	Scrap fabrics are disposed in the waste bin	82.6	17.4	Agreed
8.	Scrap fabrics are burnt	91.3	8.7	Agreed
9.	Scrap fabrics are used as dusters in dusting sewing machine	78.3	21.7	Agreed

Table 1 reveals that items: 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, and 9 have their percentage ranges above 50% and this shows that their responses are above the cutoff point while items: 4 and 5 have their percentage range below 50% and are therefore below the cutoff point. Items 4 and 5 which states that scrap fabrics are recycled and sold respectively were disagreed on while other items were agreed. This implies that scrap fabric is packed in bags and stored in shops, used in making patchworks, used in sewing babies' wears, used as rags in shops, disposed in the waste bin, burnt and used as dusters in dusting sewing machines.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution on responses of ways tailors dispose scrap fabrics.

S/N	Item statement	Yes (%)	No (%)	Remark
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1.	Scrap fabrics are thrown in the waste bin	86.9	13.1	Agreed
2.	Scrap fabrics are thrown in the gutter	17.4	82.6	Disagreed
3.	Scrap fabrics are disposed in the farm	21.7	78.3	Disagreed
4.	Scrap fabrics are buried in the ground	21.7	78.3	Disagreed
5.	Scrap fabrics are burnt	90.0	10.0	Agreed
6.	Fabric scraps are thrown away when it is raining	30.4	69.6	Disagreed
7.	Fabric scraps are thrown along the street at night	39.1	60.9	Disagreed
8.	Fabric scraps are thrown in the gully	78.3	21.7	Agreed
9.	Fabric scraps are packed and dropped on the road where ESWAMA vehicle collect them	100	0	Agreed
10.	Fabric scraps are used to fill the landfill	8.7	91.3	Disagreed

Table 2 reveals that items: 1, 5, 8 and 9 have their percentage ranges above 50% and this shows that their responses are above the cutoff point while items: 2, 3, 4, 6, 7 and 10 have their percentage range below 50% and are therefore below the cutoff point. This implies that the respondents agreed that fabric scraps are thrown in the waste bin, in the gully, burnt and are packed and dropped on the road where ESWAMA vehicle collect them. Meanwhile other items like Fabric scraps are thrown in the gutter, disposed in the farm, buried in the ground, thrown away when it is raining, thrown along the street at night and used to fill the landfill were disagreed on.

Table 3: Percentage Distribution on responses of possible outcomes of indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric.

S/N	Item statement	Yes (%)	No (%)	Remark
1.	It causes environmental pollution	95.7	4.3	Agreed
2.	It causes environmental degradation	30.4	69.6	Disagreed
3.	It causes drainage blockage	78.3	21.7	Agreed
4.	It causes flooding	43.5	56.5	Disagreed
5.	It causes greenhouse gas emission	34.8	65.2	Disagreed
6.	It can lead to some health issues	65.2	34.8	Agreed
7.	It ends in landfill	65.2	34.8	Agreed
8.	It causes air pollution	69.6	30.4	Agreed
9.	It causes water pollution	52.2	47.8	Agreed

Table 3 reveals that items: 1, 3, 6, 7, 8 and 9 have their percentage above 50% and this shows that their responses are above the cutoff point while items: 2, 4 and 5 have their percentage below 50% and are therefore below the cutoff point. By implication, it can be deduced that the respondent agreed on the fact that indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric causes environmental pollution, causes drainage blockage, can lead to some health issues, ends in landfill, causes air pollution and as well as water pollution. Moreover, the respondents disagreed on the fact that indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric causes environmental degradation, flooding and greenhouse gas emission.

Percentage Distribution of responses on the assessment on the suitability of the household items produced from the scrap fabric.

S/N	Item statement	Yes (%)	No (%)	Remark
1.	Originality	96.7	03.3	Agreed
2	Uniqueness	80.4	19.6	Agreed
3	Utility	78.3	21.7	Agreed
4	Durability	83.5	16.5	Agreed
5	Neatness	84.8	15.2	Agreed
6	Finishing	95.5	04.5	Agreed

Table 4 revealed that the respondents agreed on all the items on the suitability of the household items produced from the scrap fabric in terms of originality (96.7), uniqueness (80.4), utility (78.3), durability (83.5), neatness (84.8) and finishing (95.5).

3.1. Findings of the study

- 1 Eight ways dressmakers/tailors handle scrap fabrics.
- 2 Four ways dressmakers/tailors dispose the scrap fabrics.
- 3 Six possible outcomes of indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabrics.
- 4 Household items produced using scrap fabrics was appropriate in terms of originality, uniqueness, utility, durability, neatness, and finishing.

3.2. Discussion of findings

The study revealed the percentage rating of respondents on what tailors/dressmakers do with scrap fabrics in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State. The findings of the study as presented in Table 1 indicated that seven out of the nine ways tailors/dressmakers handle scrap fabrics were accepted by the

respondents. This implies that tailors/ dressmakers in Nsukka LGA of Enugu state pack scrap fabrics in stores, use them in making patchwork, use them in sewing babies wears, use them as rags in their shops, dispose them in waste bins, burn them and use them for dusting the sewing machine. This is in agreement with Mifetu (2021) which stated that these left overs can be used for new developments and innovations for financial purposes. Also, Hamid & Al Belihy, (2020) noted that scrap fabrics can be used for producing patchworks for outfits. Sarita Devi, Vivek Singh and Parveen Punia, (2015) also supported by pointing out that cutting waste and discarded textile materials can be used in making small items of household use and clothing accessories or can be recycled. Studies have also been conducted on the use of scrap for producing household clothing items (Offiong, 2018). Meanwhile Yeboah, (2011), also conducted a study on the use of scrap for producing collages and handmade papers. The study also revealed that the respondents disagreed on the fact that scrap fabrics can be sold and recycled. This differs with the opinion of Tabassum, Abid and Gulzarin (2021) which noted that most textiles can be recycled. This difference might be based on the fact that recycling is not a common process in Nigeria.

The study revealed the percentage rating of respondents on ways tailors/dressmakers dispose scrap fabrics in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State. The findings of the study as presented in Table 2 reveals that the respondents agreed on the fact that scrap fabrics are thrown in the waste bin, in the gully, burnt and are packed and dropped on the road where ESWAMA vehicle collect them. This is in agreement with the opinion of Chirapa, & Mberengwa, (2021) which identified various methods of disposing scrap fabrics by tailors including burning, dumping and thrift work. Other items like scrap fabrics are thrown in the gutter, disposed in the farm, buried in the ground, thrown away when it is raining, thrown along the street at night and used to fill the landfill were disagreed on. This partly differs with the opinion of Rani and Jamal (2018) which stated that clothing manufacturing generates large amount of textile waste which ends up in landfills. Meanwhile, Offiong, (2018) noted that burning fabric waste causes health hazards to human beings and cause damages to the soil and they also block waterways and drainages.

The study also revealed the percentage rating of respondents on possible outcomes of indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric by tailors/dressmakers in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State. The findings of the study as presented in Table 3 reveals that the respondent agreed on the following items-

indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric causes environmental pollution, causes drainage blockage, can lead to some health issues, ends in landfill, causes air pollution and as well as water pollution. This is in agreement with the opinion of Owodiong-Idemeko & Barikpe (2016) which stated that these scraps if not properly disposed may constitute environmental problems which include blockage of channels of water resulting in flooding to the inhabitants. Meanwhile Rani and Jamal (2018) noted that the textile industry is accused of being one of the most polluting industries. As regards to this Owodiong-Idemeko & Barikpe (2016) noted that left over fabric can be a source of fuel during fire outbreak in homes which can result to loss of lives and properties. And this is why Yeboah, (2011) stated that the amount of waste generated, and its actual or potential negative effect on the environment are matters of concern to government and communities at large. Moreover, the respondents disagreed on items which states that indiscriminate disposal of scrap fabric causes environmental degradation, flooding and greenhouse gas emission. This partly differs with the opinion of Owodiong-Idemeko & Barikpe (2016) which stated that scrap fabrics may constitute environmental problems which include blockage of channels of water resulting in flooding to the inhabitants.

4. Conclusion

There has been an increase in the population of tailors/ dressmakers in our society, most of these tailors and dressmakers engage more in the practice of free-hand cutting and free-hand method of cutting is prone to producing a large amount of fabric waste. Meanwhile obtaining scrap fabric during cutting in clothing production is totally unpreventable and inevitable, if these fabrics waste are not properly managed, they possess serious threat to the individual and our environment at large. Thus a very good way of managing the scrap fabric is by producing useful household items with them, this will not only preserve our environment by reducing erosion, water contamination and air contamination but also provide financial benefits for the family when the household items are sold.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The environmental authorities in Nigeria should provide disposal site strictly for collecting fabric waste, to enable reuse of the scrap fabrics.
2. Government should create entrepreneurship centers where people will be taught and will be producing different household articles using scrap fabrics.

3. Need for awareness program, for the tailors and dressmakers in Nsukka to be brought in the know of the effect of wrong disposal of scrap fabrics in the environment.
4. Training of tailors and dressmakers in Nsukka on recycling methods is also necessary, to reduce the quantity of scrap fabrics dumped at the landfills

References

- Bakker-Edoh (2018). Pattern Drafting and Free-Hand Cutting Skills Acquisition by Informal Dressmakers and Tailors and their Apprentices in Koforidua, Ghana. An unpublished Doctorate research Thesis submitted to the Department of Fashion and Marketing, Kenyatta University, Kenya.
- Bans- Akutey, M., Aboagyewaa-Ntiri, J., & Appiah, N. A. (2024). Usage of Free Hand Cutting and Patterns in Garment Construction in Ghana. *Art and Design Review, 12, 121-136*. <http://doi.org/10.426/adr.2024.122009>
- Bullman, H. (2007). Implementing Successful School Recycling Programs <http://www.org/ref//41/40956>.
- Chirapa, A & Mberengwa, L. R. (2021). A-Level Textile Technology and Design Curriculum Compatible with Industry Requirements in Harare, Zimbabwe, *East African Journal of Education and Social Sciences 2(2) pp. 243-251*.
- El-Nouby, G. M., Azzam, H. A., Hohamed, S. T., El-sheikl M. N. (2005). Textile waste – material recycling: Ways and Means. *Textile Processing: State of the Art and Future Developments, 2(5), 394-407*. Retrieved September 27, 2010, from <http://bgd.ifashion.co.za/downloads/1208/gamall1>.
- Erim, C. M., Okon, G. J., & Ojong, R. A. (2023). Skill Acquisition Training and Unemployment Reduction among Youths in Cross River State, Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Education (KJED) 3(2) pp. 173-184*.
- Hamid, A. S. & Al Belihy, S. M. (2020). Fabric Collage: The Beautiful Fabric from Scraps and Re-dress for the Environmental sustainability. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education 10(1) pp. 44-57*

- Koca, E. (2019). Artistic Studies on Design Development with Fabric Scraps in the Context of Sustainable Fashion. *The research Journal of costume culture* 27(6) pp. 654-665.
- Kavitha, R. & Sagar, S. (2022). Employee Challenges and Opportunities in Tailoring Industry. *Futuristic Trends in Management IIP Proceedings, Vol.2 Book 5, Part 2, Chapter 2.*
- Mifetu, G.M. (2021). Possible Ways of Minimizing Fabric Waste: A Case Study of KAD Manufacturing Limited, Ghana. Retrieved from <https://etd.ohiolink.edu>.
- Mitchell, G. (2020). <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/sustainability.asp>.
- Offiong, P. E. D. (2018). Production of Household Clothing Items using Fabric Waste for Homemakers in Cross River State. An unpublished M.Ed thesis submitted to the Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education.
- Owodiong-Idemeko, B. M & Barikpe, L. A (2016). Innovative Ability in Utilization of Fabric Scraps by Fashion Designers for Family Sustainability in Lagos State Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Benchmark (IJEb) eISSN: 2489-0170 pISSN: 2489-4162*
- Rani, S & Jamal, Z. (2018). Recycling Textile Waste for Environmental Protection. *International Journal of Home Science* 4(1) pp. 164-168
- Sensis, P. T. Y (2019). The Difference between a Tailor and a Dressmaker <https://www.yellowpages.Com.au/articles/clothing-alterations-mending>.
- Tabassum, T., Abid, A. and Gulzarin , I. (2021). Recycling of Waste Textiles through Fabric Collage Techniques into Eco-Friendly Products of Useful Accessories Using Scrap Fabrics. *Science international (Lahore)*, 33(4), 297-299.
- Yeboah, R. (2011). Waste Fabric that can be used to Produce Handmade Papers when combined with the Paper Mulberry Bark. An unpublished Report on thesis submitted to the school of post Graduate studies, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi.

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